

Spatial dynamics of savanna termite mounds: implications for heterogeneity

Andrew B Davies^{1*}, SR Levick², GP Asner³, MP Robertson¹, BJ van Rensburg⁴ and CL Parr⁵

¹Centre for Invasion Biology, Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria, South Africa, ²Max Planck-Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, Germany, ³Department of Global Ecology, Carnegie Institution, Stanford, USA ⁴School of Biological Sciences, University of Queensland, Australia, ⁵Department of Ecology, University of Liverpool, UK
*e-mail address: abdavies@zoology.up.ac.za

Spatial heterogeneity

- Heterogeneity is a key driver of biodiversity
- The focus of conservation is now on processes rather than specific species
- An understanding of factors driving biodiversity is of paramount importance for effective conservation

Termites mounds in African savannas

- Induce heterogeneity by concentrating nutrients
- Create nutrient rich hotspots with higher vegetation diversity, biomass and nutritional value
- Concentrate herbivore (mammalian and insect) distributions
- We need a better understanding of their dynamics

Digital elevation model obtained from LIDAR imagery showing clear patterns in termite mound (small black dots) distribution across the N'waswitshaka river catchment (red areas are higher in elevation, blue are lower)

Key Question

What drives the spatial patterns of termite mound densities and distributions?

Methods

Mapping mounds

- Study conducted in southern Kruger National Park
- Used LiDAR imagery from the Carnegie Airborne Observatory to map termite mounds across an entire river catchment
- Investigated effects of several abiotic variables (mean annual precipitation, soil type, mound height, percentage woody cover and fire return interval) on mound densities and structure (height)

Data analysis

- Three spatial scales (entire catchment, vegetation landscapes, 53 crests within the catchment)
- Generalised linear and mixed effects models applied

Termite mound in African savanna

Mounds act as nutrient hotspots and are therefore heavily grazed

Results and Discussion

Landscape patterning

- Mounds are evenly spaced at small scales (<60m), otherwise clustered
- Located on crests, avoid inundation
- Crests are otherwise nutrient poor, mounds provide important nutrients

Ripley's K function: mounds are clustered above 60m and over-dispersed below this threshold

The clustering of mounds occurs on crests where they are over-dispersed

Crest (fine-scale) patterns

- Bimodal density pattern with rainfall
- Larger (taller) mounds correlated with density, where conditions are good for termites (dry, nutrient rich areas), they occur at high numbers
- Possibly create a positive feedback loop, enhancing already nutrient rich savanna
- Similar trend with woody cover
- Clay level (soil type) important, termites need a balance for mound construction but not water logging

Drivers of termite mound densities: mean annual precipitation, mound height, % woody cover on crests and soil type were important determinants

Acknowledgements: Application of the CAO data in South Africa is made possible by the Andrew Mellon Foundation, Grantham Foundation for the Protection of the Environment and the endowment of the Carnegie Institution for Science. The C-I-B, University of Pretoria and SANParks are also thanked for funding, academic and logistical support.